

DESIGNING VOCABULARY TASKS FOR BEGINNERS OF ENGLISH AS A FOREIGN LANGUAGE

Boymurodova Barno Elmurod qizi¹

¹ Termez State University Foreign Filology 201 group
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5815160>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 20th December 2021

Accepted: 25th December 2021

Online: 30th December 2021

KEY WORDS

Vocabulary list, type of memory, senses, repeating, type of beginners, mind map.

ABSTRACT

This article briefly describes the right way of designing vocabulary tasks, gives idea of what teachers need to pay attention while giving vocabulary to learners.

“A word is a “Brick” in the construction of a building, whereas the building is the language and the construction is the study” says famous translator Kato Lomb.¹ For a building it is important to have a steady and strong brick. Similarly for a language, the word should be a reliable and understandable form of expression.

In English one single word has several meanings. It is necessary to acquaint learners with the most frequent ones. Nowadays learning by heart new words is traditional method, which is used by teachers all around the world. But in my opinion, this method is not suitable because some words, which are learned by repeating from vocabulary list, can easily be forgotten next day. In fact, we don't speak in individual words, we speak in phrases. But if you memorized not phrases, but words, then in order to say something in English,

you will use the Russian phrase translating each word separately.

Importantly, to memorize any word recommended using all types of memory:

- Visual, which is trained by reading and writing words;
- Auditory, which develops when a word is perceived by ear;
- Logical, which is presupposed the preliminary work of thinking by association.

According to the Great Russian teacher K.D.Ushinsky² for a perfect memorization of something is that you need to bring as many senses as possible: eyes, ear, voice, feeling for muscular movements and even, if possible, smell and taste to take part in the act of memorization. Ushinsky pointed out that with such good assistance of all organs in the act of assimilation, you will defeat the laziest memory.

The wide range of vocabulary games and tasks means that it is not hard to begin learning. Our goal is to help to choose that one that suits their learning style.

It is essential to repeat every word. It will be quicksand of short-term memory and soon forgotten. It is important to choose vocabulary that is connected to learners' lives and can be easily applied to their speech. In this case, beginners can be kids, teens or adults.

Kids love to learn about the things that surround them. At young age, kids still do not perceive language as a system. For them, English is a lot of new words. To ensure that the topic is learned with maximum efficiency, it is better to learn English words for children with visual materials. Large colorful pictures are the best solution. I realized that to help children to learn the words faster, I need to play a simple game with them, which is very simple and consisting of questions. For example, you can ask: Is plum red or blue? The kid must answer by naming the desired color.

Teens prefer to choose vocabulary that helps them to understand the books they read and the lyrics of music they listen. The main focus in the study should be on their interest. I think I have to say that turning vocabulary learning into their exciting hobby is the best solution. It should not be "through force", but "with joy"! And, of course, the usual lessons alone will not help here. Teenagers need more than school lessons, textbooks and dictionaries. Like more specifically English movies, TV series and songs should be added to their learning program. Konstantin Stanislavsky³ claimed that nothing can be taught, everything can

only be learned. Our goal is to motivate and guide them.

Adults need common words and phrases of both a personal and business level that will help them improve their communication skills. In adulthood, we perceive everything much more thoughtfully and, most importantly, we understand how we can use this knowledge and skills in work or in life. I suppose I would have to maintain that it is best to combine learning with special exercises. Games such as Bingo, Password, and Concentration greatly simplify the "active discussion of meaning", when purposeful problem solving contributes to the accumulation of "passing" vocabulary. A person may not even realize that he is memorizing new words.

Tony Buzana renowned writer, lecturer and consultant worked out "Mind Map". The Mind Map is an alternative to tradition methods of processing and transmitting information (notes). This choice is more productive, since it has a natural psychological basis, and definitely, it turns the beginners into an active creator of their own knowledge. The psychological basis of the Mind Map is associative thinking.

It is enough to reproduce in memory one object of this information card, and it will pull in a chain dozens of interrelated facts, events, and sensations. This is how multidimensional associative thinking arises, which allows you to see not just an object of the surrounding world in itself, but in interconnection with other objects. This is how Mind Map works.

Buzan attaches almost the main importance to highlighting the keyword of

the associative chain. To depict the central idea, you can use drawings, pictures.

The main branches are connected to the central idea, and the branches of the second, third, etc. Orders are connected to the main branches. The branches should be curved, not straight (like the branches of a tree). Only one keyword is written above each line - branch. For better memorization and assimilation, it is advisable to use drawings, pictures, associations about each

word. The result of the work is an individual product of one person or one group. Expresses individual possibilities, creates space for creativity.

It can be concluded Games are an inherent tool of studying, they allow learners practice, create experiences and break away from lesson atmosphere that could otherwise be tedious. Moreover, games can increase brain activity at any age.

REFERENCES:

- 1) Беляева, Л. А. Интерактивные средства обучения иностранному языку. Интерактивная доска: учебное пособие для среднего профессионального образования / Л. А. Беляева. — Москва: Издательство Юрайт, 2021. — 157 с. — (Профессиональное образование). — ISBN 978-5-534-11037-1. — Текст: электронный // ЭБС Юрайт [сайт]. — URL: <https://urait.ru/bcode/476011>
- 2) Комаров, А. С. Методика обучения английскому языку. Игры и пьесы: учебное пособие для вузов / А. С. Комаров. — 3-е изд., перераб. и доп. — Москва: Издательство Юрайт, 2021. — 156 с. — (Высшее образование). — ISBN 978-5-534-06427-8. — Текст: электронный // ЭБС Юрайт [сайт]. — URL: <https://urait.ru/bcode/472878>
- 3) Котик-Фридгут, Б. С. Психология обучения иностранным языкам: как учить язык, чтобы выучить: учебное пособие для вузов / Б. С. Котик-Фридгут. — Москва: Издательство Юрайт, 2021. — 145 с. — (Высшее образование). — ISBN 978-5-534-14197-9. — Текст: электронный // ЭБС Юрайт [сайт]. — URL: <https://urait.ru/bcode/468056>
- 4) Методика обучения иностранному языку: учебное пособие для среднего профессионального образования / О. И. Трубицина [и др.]; ответственный редактор О. И. Трубицина. — Москва: Издательство Юрайт, 2021. — 384 с. — (Профессиональное образование). — ISBN 978-5-534-11656-4. — Текст: электронный // ЭБС Юрайт [сайт]. — URL: <https://urait.ru/bcode/476372>